

A NOTE ON RAMAN SCATTERING OF SILICATE SOLUTIONS.

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A large number of sodium silicates containing different proportions of silica can be obtained. Starting with the meta-silicate where the ratio between $\text{Na}_2\text{O} : \text{SiO}_2$ is as 1 : 1, one can easily prepare solutions of increasing silica content even up to the ratio 1 : 4. In view of the large variation in the proportion of silica which is possible, the question of fixing the molecular nature of these solutions becomes a complicated one. The question is further complicated by the hydrolysis undergone by the silicate solutions. The extent of hydrolysis was studied by Kohlrausch (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1893, 12, 773) from measurements of electrical conductivity and by Kahlenberg (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1898, 2, 77), and Lunis (*Annalen*, 1897, 60, 531) from freezing point lowering measurements. They found that the alkali silicates were largely hydrolysed in aqueous solutions giving rise to an amount of free silica which tended to pass into the colloidal state. Bogue (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 2575), however, showed that the degree of hydrolysis as determined by E. M. F. measurements was unexpectedly low and was at variance with the conclusions drawn from conductivity and other measurements.

The sodium silicates have been exhaustively studied by Harman (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 44). He concludes that the solutions with the ratio 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 only contain definite salts namely Na_2SiO_3 and NaHSiO_3 . Above the ratio 1 : 2, as the proportion of silica increases colloidal silica is in evidence. In concentrated solutions of the higher ratios, a larger colloidal aggregate containing both sodium and silica has been found.

In previous papers by one of us (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 706), it has been inferred that the silicate solutions contain colloidal micelles and that the amount of the colloid increases rapidly after the ratio 1 : 3 is exceeded.

Although in the literature many references to sodium silicates like Na_3SiO_2 , $\text{Na}_2\text{Si}_2\text{O}_5$, NaHSiO_3 , $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_{11}$, Na_4SiO_4 etc., exist the only sodium silicate whose molecular composition is definitely known is the meta-silicate. In the present paper, therefore, the Raman scattering of the meta-silicate as well as that of the higher ratio solutions have been investigated. For the purposes of comparison the scattering of a dialysed

solution of silicic acid has also been studied. If the higher ratio sodium silicate solutions be allied in molecular nature to the sodium meta-silicate, all these solutions might give a common Raman shift characteristic of the common ingredient between them all. If on the other hand the higher ratio silicate solutions contain an appreciable amount of fine grained colloidal silica, they might behave with respect to Raman scattering in a manner analogous to that of a dialysed solution of silicic acid. As will be seen in the following pages, the same Raman shift, as is obtained with the meta-silicate solution, is also obtained with the higher ratio silicate solutions. but with increase in the proportion of silicate in these solutions there is a large amount of general or Rayleigh scattering which takes away the sharpness of the Raman bands. This behaviour is expected if the higher ratio silicate solutions are to contain increasing amounts of colloidal matter.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following solutions were investigated :

1. Solution of sodium meta-silicate. (2) Solution of sodium silicate containing $\text{Na}_2\text{O} : \text{SiO}_2$ in the ratio 1 : 2. (3) Solution of sodium silicate of ratio 1 : 4. (4) Dialysed solution of silicic acid.

The last named solution was prepared by Graham's method. The concentration of the solution was 10% with respect to its silica content. The other solutions were carefully analysed and were made equivalent such that all the solutions contained the same amount of silica, *viz.*, 24.88 g. per 100 g. of the solution. All the solutions were protected from atmospheric carbon dioxide.

The exciting source used was the mercury arc, the ultra-violet portion being cut off by the interposition of a glass plate. The tube containing the solution was placed at the focal plane of an ellipsoidal vessel and was kept cool by circulating a stream of water. To get a good reflecting surface, the interior of the vessel was plated and polished.

The exciting line in each case was taken to be the 4358 mercury line. Microphotographic prints were taken from the plates some of which are reproduced in the accompanying diagram. In the case of the Na_2SiO_3 and the 1 : 2 ratio solution, fairly sharp peaks corresponding to the modified lines were obtained, but in the case of the other two solutions sharpness was absent. To locate the position of the modified lines a somewhat magnified microphotograph was taken. Figures 2—5 refer to these magnified microphotographs of the meta-silicate, of the 1 : 2 ratio solution, of

4309
4358
4408

FIG. 1.
Sodium meta-silicate.

4418 4358 4309

FIG. 2.
Sodium meta-silicate.

4107.7 4358 4306.9

FIG. 3.
1 : 2 ratio silicate soln.

FIG. 4.
1 : 4 ratio silicate soln.

FIG. 5.
Colloidal silicic acid.

the 1 : 4 ratio solution and of the dialysed silicic acid solution respectively. The values are given in the following table.

	Solution.	Exciting line.		Modified line.		$\Delta\nu$.	λ .
		λ .	ν .	λ .	ν_1 .		
				4309	23208A.S.	261	38'3 μ
1	Na_2SiO_3	4358	22947	4408	22686	261	38'3
				4309'4	23206	259	38'6
2	1 : 2 Solution	4358	22947	4407'7	22687	260	38'5
				4308'9	23209	262	38'2
3	1 : 4 ..	4358	22947	4408'1	22685	262	38'2
				4309'2	23207	260	38'5
4	Colloidal silicic acid	4358	22947	4407'6	22688	259	38'6

Sodium meta-silicate gives a Raman shift equal to $\Delta\nu = 261 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and exactly the same modified line is given by the two higher ratio silicate solutions. It is evident, therefore, that there is some constituent which is common to all these solutions. It is interesting to recall that the shift as obtained in the present experiments corresponds to one of the modified lines for quartz obtained by Krishnan (*Nature*, 1928, 122, 477) and also by Czenny (*Z. Physik*, 1929, 53, 317). Probably this shift is due to SiO_2 group which is present in all these systems. Although the plate obtained with 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 silicate solutions give the same modified lines, they differ to a very marked extent so far as the sharpness of the bands is concerned. In the case of the 1 : 4 ratio solution, there was pronounced general scattering similar to that obtained with the dialysed silicic acid sol. So far as these experiments go, it seems reasonable to infer that colloidal matter increases quite rapidly.

The measurement of the photographic density of the plates at a fixed distance from the exciting lines for the various solutions is likely to yield some interesting information about the colloidal content of the higher ratio solutions. Further work on the above lines is in progress.

In conclusion we wish to express our thanks to Professor Kamta Prosad for his kind interest in the work and to Mr. B. N. Ghosh for help with the microphotometer.